

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Glutaric Acid by Cerium(IV) Ion in Acidic Medium

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Kinetic study of oxidation of glutaric acid by Ce(IV) ion in aqueous solution of sulphuric acid shows that the reaction follows first order kinetics in both Ce(IV) and glutaric acid and the over all reaction order ascertained is two. The specific rate constant increases with an increase in the concentration of glutaric acid. Effects of hydrogen ions concentration and temperature have been examined in details. Activation parameters have also been computed. The experimental findings are consistent with the mechanism involving rapid reversible formation of an activated complex between Ce(IV) and glutaric acid followed by a rate determining step involving C-C bond fission.

THE Ce(IV) ion is one of the strongest oxidising agents known in aqueous solution with an oxidation potential of 1.43 ± 0.05 volts in 1-8 N sulphuric acid¹. The common valencies of cerium in cerium salts are three and four in which the probable unhybridised electronic configurations² are $5s^2 5p^6 4d^1 05f^1$ and $5s^2 5p^6 4d^1 0$ respectively. So it seems that monomeric cerium (IV) is one electron oxidant. The first review on cerium ion oxidation appeared in 1942³. The oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by Ce(IV) was studied by Dayal and Bakore⁴. The oxidation of isobutyric acid by Ce(IV) was studied by Balkrishna and Bharat Singh⁵. A survey of the literature shows that a systematic kinetic study of the oxidation of aliphatic dicarboxylic acids like oxalic, malonic⁶⁻⁹, succinic and glutaric acid has not received any attention so far.

Materials and Procedure : All the reagents were of highest purity available. The stock solution of ceric sulphate was prepared by dissolving a weighed quantity of it in the calculated amount of sulphuric acid. The reacting substances were brought to the thermostat, which maintained the temperature at a constant value within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ and then rapidly mixed. Aliquots were withdrawn at known intervals of time and the reaction was quenched by adding ice-cold distilled water and the unconsumed Ce(IV) was estimated with a standard solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin as an indicator.

Results and Discussion

Dependence of Reaction on Oxidant : In order to determine the order of reaction with respect to the oxidant, the reaction was studied at different initial

concentrations of ceric sulphate and at fixed concentrations of other reactants. The reaction follows first order kinetics in Ce(IV). Table-1 contains the representative results obtained in a set of the reaction.

TABLE 1

$[H_2SO_4] = 0.15M$; $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 2.50 \times 10^{-3}M$ $[Glutaric\ acid] = 1.50 \times 10^{-2}M$
Temp. = 60°

Time in minutes	Volume of ferrous ammonium sulphate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) equivalent to ceric sulphate required for 5 ml of reaction mixture	$K_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
00	4.80	
5	4.65	6.31
15	4.37	6.18
30	3.99	6.15
45	3.66	6.01
60	3.34	6.04
80	2.96	6.04
100	2.63	5.99

average value of $k_1 = 6.09 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$

the value from the graph of $k_1 = 6.10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$

The results of other studies done at different concentrations of Ce(IV) are given in Table-2. The K_1 (first order rate constant) values obtained from the

* All correspondence to be made.

slopes of the curves were also given in Table-1 and show good agreement with average K_1 values. Contrary to our expectation, the K_1 values decrease with increasing initial concentration of Ce(IV). Shorter¹⁰ and Bhagwat⁶ also observed similar effects in their studies.

Dependence of Reaction on Reductant Concentration : The rate of reaction with respect to reductant was studied at different concentrations of glutaric acid by isolation method. Pseudo first order rate constant K_1 values for different concentrations are recorded in Table-2. A perusal of data of Table-2 indicates that K_1 values are directly proportional to the concentration of glutaric acid showing thereby that the reaction also follows first order in glutaric acid. The values of second order rate constant (K_2) determined from $K_1/[glutaric\ acid]$ are practically constant as recorded in Table-2.

TABLE 2

Temp. = 60°; [H ₂ SO ₄] = 0.15 M			
[Ce(SO ₄) ₂] × 10 ³ M	[Glutaric acid] × 10 ³ M	$K_1 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	$K_2 \times 10^3$ mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
1.50	1.50	8.44	—
2.00	1.50	7.36	—
2.50	1.50	6.10	—
3.00	1.50	4.31	—
3.50	1.50	3.26	—
2.50	0.50	2.05	4.10
2.50	1.00	4.05	4.05
2.50	1.50	6.10	4.06
2.50	2.00	7.45	3.72
2.50	2.50	9.50	3.80

average value of $k_2 = 3.94 \times 10^{-12}$ mole⁻¹ mine⁻¹

Dependence of Reaction on Sulphuric Acid Concentration : In order to study the role of sulphuric acid in sulphuric acid-Ceric sulphate system, the reaction was carried out at different concentrations of sulphuric acid between the temperature range from 40 to 65°. It was found that the plot of K_1 Vs. $\frac{1}{[H_2SO_4]^2}$

does not give a straight line upto 55° but at 60° the relationship holds good (vide Table-3) which is similar to the oxidation of α -hydroxy acid by Ce(IV) ion^{11,12}. But in the oxidation of malonic acid by Ce(IV) in perchloric acid^{13,14} medium, the rate increases with increase in H⁺ ion concentration while in the oxidation of α -carboxylic acid¹⁵ by Ce(IV) in presence of sulphuric acid, the rate decreases as the H⁺ ion concentration increases. These findings are similar to the oxidation of glycolic acid¹⁶ by Ce(IV) in presence of

sulphuric acid. In the present study the effect of sulphuric acid over a wide range could not be studied because marked changes in the rate are produced probably due to the formation of higher ceric sulphate complex [Ce(SO₄)₄]¹⁶.

Further in order to confirm the effect of sulphuric acid on the reaction rate, the experiments were performed at constant bisulphate concentration by using NaHSO₄-H₂SO₄ mixture. It was observed that on increasing the NaHSO₄ concentration, the rate decreases.

TABLE 3

Temp. 60°

[Ce(SO ₄) ₂] = 2.0 × 10 ⁻³ M,		[glutaric acid] = 1.50 × 10 ⁻³ M			
[H ₂ SO ₄] M	0.08	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25
$k_1 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	8.25	7.40	6.10	5.72	3.75

Dependence of Reaction on Temperature : To determine the energy parameters, the reaction was carried out at different temperatures. The values of energy of activation (ΔE) and entropy of activation (ΔS) are 12.42 K cal/mole and -41.51 e.u. respectively. The values of free energy (ΔF) and frequency factor (A) come out to be 25.35 K cal/mole and 17.20×10^9 litre mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ respectively.

Stoichiometry studies have shown that in Ce(IV)-glutaric acid reaction about 14 equivalents of Ce(IV) are consumed per mole of glutaric acid. Formic acid has been identified and tested by chromatographic technique.

The intermediate product, an aldehyde, is oxidised by Ce(IV) giving final product through very fast subsequent steps as shown in the oxidation of malic acid by quinivalent vanadium¹⁷.

The plot of $1/K_1$ Vs $1/[glutaric\ acid]$ is straight line and cuts the $1/K_1$ axis at a certain distance suggesting the activated complex formation between Ce(IV) and glutaric acid. The activated complex decomposes through chain mechanism. The chain mechanism involving free radical is evident from the negative value of entropy of activation and frequency factor¹⁸ of the order less than 10^{10} sec⁻¹. The coordination number of Ce(IV) is being six and on the basis of above kinetic behaviour of the oxidation of glutaric acid by Ce(IV)

the following mechanism has been proposed.

On the basis of the above proposed mechanism and other experimental facts, the rate of disappearance of ceric sulphate comes out to be :

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = K[\text{Ce(IV)}]$$

This rate expression is quite consistent without kinetic data and here K is the rate constant observed practically.

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